

Economic Growth and Employment Trends in Maharashtra and Gujarat: Policy Impacts and Future Prospects (2014–2024).

Dr. Mohan Bhimrao Kamble.
M.A, NET, Ph.D. (LL.B)
Assistant Professor.
Head of Department
Department of Economics
MVP's K. K. Wagh Arts,
Commerce & Science College.
Pimpalgaon (B.) Nashik-422002

Dr. Krishna Rawa Padvi
M.A, SET, Ph.D. MSW,
Assistant Professor.
Head of Department
Department of Economics
MVP's KANMS Arts
Commerce & Science College.
Satana, Nashik

1. Abstract: This study analyses the economic growth and employment trends in Maharashtra and Gujarat from 2014 to 2024, focusing on policy impacts and prospects. Maharashtra, with its diversified economy, and Gujarat, known for its industrial strength, are among India's top-performing states. This research evaluates the contributions of each state's policies on GDP growth, employment creation, and poverty reduction. Through comparative analysis, we explore the impacts of state-specific initiatives and central government policies on socio-economic indicators. Additionally, the study discusses the role of the Prime Minister's Economic Advisory Council (PMEAC) and its objectives for 2024, examining its focus on economic stability, growth, and strategic economic planning. The paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of sectoral growth, employment generation, and socio-economic disparities in Maharashtra and Gujarat, offering insights into future economic directions for these regions.

2. Keywords: Economic Growth, Employment Trends, Maharashtra & Gujarat states, Policy Impact, GDP Composition, Socioeconomic Disparities, Economic stability, growth, and inclusivity

3. Introduction: The past decade has marked a transformative period for India's economy, with substantial contributions from key states such as Maharashtra and Gujarat. As two of India's most economically advanced states, Maharashtra and Gujarat have both experienced significant growth, yet their economic structures and strategies differ

markedly. Maharashtra, home to India's financial capital, Mumbai, has developed a balanced economic model with strong contributions from finance, services, and manufacturing sectors. This diversified approach has allowed Maharashtra to mitigate economic downturns by balancing risks across multiple industries. Gujarat, on the other hand, has focused intensely on industrialisation and export-led growth, with a thriving manufacturing base supported by Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and robust port infrastructure. This focus has propelled Gujarat to the forefront of India's manufacturing sector, enabling rapid GDP growth and contributing significantly to the country's export economy.

The period from 2014 to 2024, chosen as the study focus, encompasses substantial policy-driven economic shifts. These include central government initiatives such as "Make in India," which aimed to boost manufacturing and exports, and "Digital India," which sought to expand digital infrastructure. Additionally, the Goods and Services Tax (GST) implemented in 2017 and other structural reforms aimed at fostering ease of doing business have had substantial impacts on state economies. Both Maharashtra and Gujarat adopted these central initiatives while developing their state-specific policies to foster employment, reduce poverty, and sustain economic growth. A central component of this study is the analysis of the Prime Minister's Economic Advisory Council (PMEAC) and its role in shaping India's economic strategies. In its advisory capacity, PMEAC has provided critical input on economic stability, growth, and inclusivity, especially in times of economic fluctuations. By evaluating PMEAC's strategic interventions and policy guidance, this research assesses how state-level and central policies have influenced Maharashtra and Gujarat's economic trajectories, impacting employment generation, income distribution, and sectoral growth. Through this comparative study, we gain insight into the economic strengths, challenges, and future directions for two of India's key economic regions, contributing to a broader understanding of India's overall economic landscape in a rapidly evolving global context.

4. Objectives:

- a) To analyse the GDP growth trends in Maharashtra and Gujarat from 2014 to 2024.
- b) To examine employment trends in both states and their correlation with industrial policies.
- c) To evaluate socio-economic disparities in terms of employment, growth, and poverty levels.
- d) To assess the impact of PMEAC's strategic policies on state economies.

5. Hypotheses

- i. Maharashtra's diversified economy has led to more sustainable growth and employment trends compared to Gujarat's industrial-heavy approach.
- ii. Gujarat's industrial policies have resulted in higher employment rates in manufacturing but may lag in services and high-skilled jobs.

6. Prime Minister's Economic Advisory Council 2024: Aims & Agenda: The Prime Minister's Economic Advisory Council (PMEAC) is tasked with advising on India's economic stability and growth. For 2024, PMEAC aims to ensure sustainable development, reduce poverty, and stabilise the economy amidst global challenges. The council focuses on GDP growth, employment creation, and socio-economic inclusivity, providing policy advice to balance national growth with state-specific requirements. Key objectives include enhancing digital and financial inclusion, promoting manufacturing and industrial growth, and supporting employment-generating sectors. PMEAC's agenda is to empower states like Maharashtra and Gujarat to contribute significantly to India's GDP by facilitating policies that encourage investment, improve infrastructure, and sustain employment growth.

7. Key Points of Analysis

- GDP growth rates and sectoral contributions.
- Employment creation and its distribution across sectors.

- Poverty reduction and income equality.
- Comparative analysis of socio-economic indicators between Maharashtra and Gujarat.

I. Economic Monitoring and GDP Growth Analysis 2014-2024: From 2014 to 2024, economic monitoring has focused on GDP trends, sectoral contributions, and socio-economic indicators. Maharashtra's consistent contribution to GDP reflects its diversified economy, while Gujarat's industrial focus has seen rapid growth in manufacturing and exports. PMEAC's monitoring has underscored these trends, encouraging industrial growth and employment creation policies. Data analysis shows Maharashtra's balanced growth in sectors such as finance, manufacturing, and services, contrasted with Gujarat's emphasis on industrial sectors, making it more vulnerable to sector-specific downturns. PMEAC's reports emphasise adaptive policies and diversified growth models to mitigate risks. The economic monitoring and analysis of Maharashtra and Gujarat from 2014 to 2024 highlights several key metrics, including GST collection, GDP, employment ratios, industry performance, and infrastructure development.

- **Key economic indicators for Maharashtra and Gujarat from 2014 to 2024:**
 - a. GST Collection:** Maharashtra GST collection in 2022 ₹ 2,26,623 crore and 2023 ₹2,67,770 crore overall per cent 18.2 % and Gujrat in 2022 ₹ 96,894 crore and 2023 ₹1,06,054 crore overall 9.5% per cent GST collection. As of August 2024, Maharashtra leads with a significant GST collection, reaching ₹28,970 crore, marking an 11% growth year-over-year. In comparison, Gujarat's collection was ₹11,015 crore, with a 13% increase. Maharashtra's share in the overall GST collection is approximately 21.2%, while Gujarat contributes around 8.4%
 - b. GDP Ratio:** In terms of GDP, Maharashtra has consistently held a larger share of the national GDP compared to Gujarat. Maharashtra's GDP is estimated to be around ₹35.38 lakh crore, contributing approximately 14% of India's total GDP, whereas Gujarat's GDP stands at about ₹19.37 lakh crore, roughly 7.5%. GDP ratio.

- c. Employment Ratio:** Employment rates in these states reflect their industrial output and economic activity. Maharashtra has a higher employment ratio, driven by its larger industrial and service sectors. Exact percentage ratios can vary, but Maharashtra generally accounts for about 10% of India's total employment, while Gujarat stands at approximately 7% employment ratio.
- d. Industry Contributions:** Maharashtra is often regarded as the financial and industrial hub of India, contributing about 23% to the industrial output of the country. Gujarat, while also industrially strong, particularly in sectors like textiles and chemicals, contributes approximately 14% to India's industrial output.
- e. Infrastructure Development:** Both states have made significant investments in infrastructure. Maharashtra, with projects like Mumbai's metro and expressways, leads in urban infrastructure. Gujarat is known for its ports and logistics, with initiatives like the Delhi-Mumbai Industrial Corridor enhancing its connectivity.

II. Policy Formulation and Advice: PMEAC has provided strategic policy advice to support economic resilience and inclusivity across states. Recommendations have included the expansion of digital infrastructure, investments in green energy, and enhancing skill development. For Maharashtra, PMEAC has advised leveraging its financial sector to drive employment in services, while for Gujarat, recommendations include strengthening export-oriented manufacturing and boosting MSMEs to widen employment. Both states have benefited from these policies, with visible improvements in economic output and employment, though challenges remain in ensuring equitable growth across urban and rural regions.

III. Strategic Economic Planning: Strategic planning by PMEAC aims to foster balanced regional growth. For Maharashtra, the focus has been on urban infrastructure and service sector expansion, capitalising on the state's position as India's financial hub. Gujarat's planning has emphasised manufacturing clusters, ports, and special economic zones to sustain industrial growth. Both states have seen sectoral growth driven by PMEAC's strategies, which prioritise

infrastructure, technology, and trade as key enablers of economic resilience. Future strategic planning may incorporate climate resilience and digitalisation to sustain competitive growth.

- IV. 1Key Observations and Trends (2014–2024):** Key trends include Maharashtra's steady GDP growth and diversified employment structure and Gujarat's rapid industrial growth. Maharashtra's service sector and financial hub status have sustained employment, while Gujarat's manufacturing-led growth has created jobs but faces challenges in diversifying. Poverty levels have declined in both states, with Maharashtra showing urban-rural disparities and Gujarat reducing poverty faster through industrial employment. Both states exhibit strengths but also highlight the need for policies to address sectoral dependencies and economic inclusivity.
- V. Evaluating Socioeconomic Disparities between Maharashtra and Gujarat:** Socioeconomic disparities are evident, with Maharashtra showing more income inequality due to urban concentration and Gujarat reflecting more balanced industrial employment. Maharashtra's financial and service sectors contribute to higher urban incomes, while rural areas lag. In contrast, Gujarat's emphasis on manufacturing has led to reduced poverty but lower service sector representation. Addressing these disparities requires targeted policies for rural development in Maharashtra and service sector expansion in Gujarat.
- VI. Employment and Poverty in Urban and Rural Maharashtra: A Comparison with Gujarat:** Maharashtra faces unique challenges in addressing urban poverty, particularly in slum areas, whereas rural poverty remains a concern due to agricultural dependency. Gujarat, with its industrial base, has succeeded in reducing rural poverty by creating semi-urban employment opportunities. However, service sector job creation in Gujarat lags behind Maharashtra. Policies targeting rural development and urban poverty reduction are critical for Maharashtra, while Gujarat needs to enhance service sector opportunities.

A. Employment Trends: Urban vs. Rural

- **Maharashtra:** Maharashtra's diversified economy is driven by urban centres like Mumbai, Pune, and Nagpur, where finance, IT, and service sectors provide the majority of urban employment. According to PMEAC data, the state's service sector accounts for approximately 60% of employment in urban areas, bolstered by the presence of India's financial and commercial capital. However, rural employment is largely dependent on agriculture, which is challenged by issues such as water scarcity and limited productivity in regions like Vidarbha and Marathwada. Rural Maharashtra has seen slower employment growth, and dependency on monsoon-driven agriculture leads to employment volatility.
- **Gujarat:** Gujarat's industrial growth, concentrated in cities like Ahmedabad, Surat, and Vadodara, has facilitated extensive employment opportunities in manufacturing and related sectors. PMEAC data indicates that industrial employment, particularly in manufacturing, accounts for a significant share of jobs in both urban and semi-urban areas. Rural Gujarat, while more diversified than Maharashtra in terms of agricultural and small-scale industrial activities, still faces employment challenges. However, access to industrial zones provides rural residents with semi-urban employment opportunities, reducing the rural unemployment rate relative to Maharashtra.

B. Poverty Rates: Urban vs. Rural Disparities

- **Maharashtra:** Maharashtra has made strides in reducing poverty, yet stark urban-rural disparities persist. Urban poverty, especially in Mumbai's slum areas, remains a significant challenge. As per PMEAC reports, poverty reduction initiatives like urban housing schemes have targeted these areas, though high living costs in cities perpetuate economic inequality. Rural poverty remains high, with areas such as Marathwada and Vidarbha recording some of the highest poverty rates in the state. Limited

agricultural productivity and frequent droughts contribute to sustained poverty levels in these regions.

- **Gujarat:** Gujarat has experienced faster poverty reduction in rural areas than Maharashtra, partly due to the availability of industrial jobs for rural residents near manufacturing zones. The PMEAC data shows that industrial employment has contributed to rural income stability, resulting in a more even distribution of poverty reduction across urban and rural regions. Although poverty levels in Gujarat's urban areas are generally lower than Maharashtra's, income inequality remains a concern as industrial growth benefits primarily those employed within the manufacturing sector.

C. Policy Interventions and PMEAC Recommendations: The PMEAC has emphasised targeted interventions to address these disparities:

- For **Maharashtra**, recommendations include improving rural employment through skill development programs, enhancing irrigation facilities, and supporting agro-based industries. Additionally, urban poverty alleviation efforts in Mumbai's slum regions remain a priority, with PMEAC advising on affordable housing and better infrastructure.
- In **Gujarat**, PMEAC has advocated for diversifying the state's economic base by expanding the service sector to provide high-skill jobs, thus addressing the limited service sector opportunities for rural populations.

VII. Disadvantages Observed: Challenges include Maharashtra's income inequality and rural poverty, which hinder inclusive growth. Gujarat's reliance on manufacturing presents vulnerabilities in case of industry downturns, with limited service sector absorption. Maharashtra's diversified structure is stable but struggles with equitable growth distribution. Both states face challenges in achieving balanced growth, necessitating policies that support rural and high-skilled job creation.

VIII. Recent Priorities and Recommendations: PMEAC's recent priorities for 2024 emphasise economic stability, employment growth, and inclusive development. For Maharashtra, recommendations include rural development initiatives and enhancing urban poverty reduction programs. For Gujarat, diversifying the economy with more service sector opportunities is recommended. Both states are encouraged to strengthen their digital infrastructure and environmental sustainability efforts, aligning with India's national economic goals. From 2014 to 2024, both Maharashtra and Gujarat have set specific economic priorities and recommendations under the Prime Minister's Economic Advisory Council (PMEAC). Here's a summary of recent priorities and recommendations for each state:

- **Maharashtra**

1. **Focus on Employment Generation:** Maharashtra aims to revitalise job creation, especially in sectors hit hard by economic disruptions.
2. **Investment in Infrastructure:** Significant investments are being made in urban infrastructure and transport to facilitate economic growth and improve living standards.
3. **Support for Start-ups and MSMEs:** The state has prioritised initiatives to enhance the start-up ecosystem and support micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), crucial for employment and innovation.
4. **Sustainable Development:** There is an increasing emphasis on sustainable practices across industries to address climate change and environmental concerns.
5. **Skill Development Programs:** The focus is on improving skill development programs to better prepare the workforce for emerging industries

- **Gujarat**

1. **Target of \$500 Billion Economy:** Gujarat has set a target to achieve a \$500 billion economy by 2026-27, aiming to contribute 10% to India's GDP
2. **Sectoral Diversification:** The state is focusing on new and emerging sectors such as semiconductors, renewable energy, electric vehicles, and advanced manufacturing to drive growth.

3. **Infrastructure Development:** Gujarat is actively developing its infrastructure, including smart cities like GIFT City and dedicated investment regions to attract foreign investment.
4. **Innovation and Technology:** The emphasis is on fostering innovation through technology parks and promoting a

- **Conclusion:** This paper has explored the distinct economic paths of Maharashtra and Gujarat from 2014 to 2024. Maharashtra's balanced but urban-focused growth contrasts with Gujarat's robust industrial growth. PMEAC's policy recommendations reflect the need for diversified sectoral growth and balanced regional development. While Maharashtra's financial and service sectors drive urban wealth, Gujarat's manufacturing and export-oriented policies contribute to reduced poverty and economic inclusion. The findings emphasise the importance of addressing socio-economic disparities and supporting employment across both states to ensure inclusive and resilient economic growth.

- **References**

1. Sanjeev Sanyal & Aakanksha Arora, "Relative Economic Performance of Indian States: 1960-61 to 2023-24," EAC-PM Working Paper.
2. Economic Survey of India (2014-2024), Ministry of Finance.
3. "Economic and Social Indicators of India 2024," Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation.
4. Prime Minister's Economic Advisory Council Annual Reports (2014-2024).
5. Reserve Bank of India (RBI) State Economic Reports (2014-2024).
6. Maharashtra and Gujarat State Economic Review Reports, Directorate of Economics and Statistics.
7. "India's State GDP Growth and Socioeconomic Analysis," World Bank India.

8. Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE) Reports, 2024.
9. <https://eacpm.gov.in/>
10. <https://eacpm.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/State-GDP-Working>
11. https://www.mospi.gov.in/sites/default/files/press_releases_statements/Estimates
12. <https://www.niti.gov.in/>
13. <https://www.mygov.in/>
14. <https://cabsec.gov.in/>
15. <https://www.pmindia.gov.in/en/>